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*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

Научно-исследовательский институт «Физики резонансных ядерных реакций» является научным учреждением, осуществляющим фундаментальные, прикладные научные исследования и инновационные разработки в области науки, техники, культуры и просвещения.

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THE IMPACT OF MODERN VIEWS OF MORAL THREATS ON YOUTH CONSCIOUSNESS

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Sabriddinova Kibriyo

Chirchik State Pedagogical University Faculty
of Humanities 2nd year student

Abstract: This article examines the impact of contemporary forms of moral threats on the minds of young people and their positive and negative aspects.

Keywords: moral threats, postmodern society, technology, youth, information explosion.

It is widely accepted that contemporary society is a largely postmodern society. Its main features: high technologies are used in production, information technologies have penetrated not only into the sphere of mass communications, but also into all spheres of social life, even into production, the software sector (electronic communication services) has become an integral part of socio-economic and cultural life, the trend of globalization in world development came into being, mass culture became a widespread social phenomenon, human consciousness, thinking and behavior, and the mentality of society changed significantly. As a result, some classical values are deformed, and in some cases they are replaced by false values. [Page 1.63]

The flow of various information in society has become so intense and multiplied that experts call it an «information explosion.» Naturally, the consequences of the explosion are not always positive, it can also bring shocks, injuries and destruction. The information explosion has become the cause of all kinds of conflicts and information attacks. The average person does not have time to digest the essence of the information that is pouring in, to separate the good from the bad, the bad from the bad, to critically analyze and evaluate it. [Page 2.51]

Some information is not sufficiently informative and of a high quality to be evaluated. Public consciousness is being manipulated through various

PR companies with the help of a selective and systematized information attack.

Various non-national ideas and views disseminated through the Internet, foreign TV channels, mobile communication systems, and other media are having a serious impact on the minds of young people. Since the early years of independence, dozens of new newspapers and magazines, private radio stations, and television studios have been established and are undergoing the process of formation. The ideological direction of these publications, the issue of morality in the published articles, is emerging as one of the most pressing problems.

These problems, which the founder and editor-in-chief of the publication must directly consider, should make the leaders of the nation — intellectuals — think. Since we are the children of this people, none of us is given the right to mock its moral values, feelings. The examples of «creation» that are constantly being published in a number of private publications, if only for a certain reason, can be understood as an attack on the national spirituality. Our colleagues who cheaply exploit and crush shame, honor, thought, and pride, which are a vivid expression of the Uzbek mentality («The man who is ashamed is dead,» «Shame is harder than death» — folk proverbs), also bear the responsibility of independence. In the pages of some private newspapers, we can find stories and tales that lead to violence, obscenity, and sensuality. [Page 3.102]

Here we are talking about the activities of non-governmental publications, and we express our attitude to the erotic stories and articles in most newspapers, so the goal of opening a newspaper is to make money, to be profitable. But this should not be considered a moral degradation of the people, a narrow worldview. However, in the pages of many private newspapers, we can find stories and tales that lead to violence, obscenity, and sensuality. Because this is a market economy. The strict conclusion of «supply and demand» surprised us. True, in a market economy, supply and demand play a large role.

But how accurate is it to define spirituality with the laws of the market? Let's remember that the great writer Abdulla Kadiri, in his novel «Days Past,» did not make the fates of Otabek and Kumush veiled, mysterious, and attractive in the pages, but, on the contrary, depicted them openly and deeply in five or six pages. No, our writer would not do this, or rather, could not do it. Because, the inner greatness, the love for the nation, the truly human virtues — modesty, honor, pride — in Abdullah Kadyri would not allow it. Such examples can be cited as much as you want. The light that illuminates such works from within is devotion to the Motherland, the people, and human love. In most of today's private publications, there is no criterion — the measure itself. For them, lack of criteria is a criterion, lack of ideas is an idea that fulfills its function. One wonders if the authors of immoral and absolutely unnational adventures were

brought up in an Uzbek environment. It is also painful that the low-quality clips and movies that are constantly broadcast on music channels convince the people, make them laugh, and when the time comes, make them cry. The so-called «yellow press» media shouts and screams on its front page, condemning the same lack of morality and culture, but on its second page, it itself destroys that same morality and culture.

In fact, it would be good if they could show other practical examples of their work as representatives of culture and spirituality. For example, by providing information about the works of art, films, and plays they have read these days, or by supporting needy families or talented but disadvantaged young people in our society, the luminaries could be the continuation and promoters of our national values. Some associate these processes with democracy. Democracy does not mean disorder. In fact, the concept of democracy is not a separate invention belonging to the West or the East. Its emergence is associated with the development of the general thinking of a conscious person, the emergence of new edges of perception.

This happened in both places at the same time. The true and unchanging content of democracy is freedom of conscience! We know very well that behind the word conscience are very delicate qualities such as patriotism, nationalism, humanity, faith, loyalty, shame, honor, modesty, and thought, colored by high spirituality. Mutual aid, community, compassion, and kindness are fundamental values that shape human nature. Virtual reality is distorting them. Virtual reality, the world of simulations, and their multiplicity on the computer have weakened the traditional views, value system, and sense of responsibility of a person who is connected to this world for the consequences of his decisions and behavior. Today's Uzbekistan was a major crossroads of the historical «Great Silk Road».

Our ancestors were scholars and virtuous people who amazed the world with their knowledge and authority. The main force that set in motion the great awakening of the East was, in fact, the leaders who emerged from among our ancestors, such as al-Khwarizmi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Al-Farabi, Imam al-Bukhari, az-Zamakhshari, at-Tirmidhi, Mirza Ulugbek, Ali Kushchi, Navoi, and Babur. What about today, are our young people living up to their grandfathers and grandmothers? Are they taking full advantage of their opportunities and powers? Of course, the children of the Motherland, who have achieved independence, are now showing the world that we have a worthy place and influence in the world, whether in the field of sports or education.

Therefore, we need to pay attention to the following aspects:

- instilling our national values in children's minds;
- Parents should encourage young people from a young age to set clear goals for themselves and create their own future;

- teaching parents to analyze information together with their children when using information sources, thus creating ideological immunity;
- to form a culture of using the media and mobile phones in children;
- prevention of Internet addiction;
- control the free time of young people, involve them in useful activities and clubs;
- teaching children to read fiction;
- Establish regular monitoring and screening of media broadcasts, interviews, and information;
- restricting and controlling the activities of Internet cafes.

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